

ISSUES OF NATIONAL ECONOMIC SECURITY IN THE CONTEXT OF GREEN ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Rustamova Maftuna Rustam qizi

TSUE "Economic security" department assistant

M.A.Buranova

Research advisor: t.f.d.Dots.

E-mail: maftunarustamova274@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10013139>

Abstract:

As countries worldwide seek to address the pressing issue of environmental sustainability, Uzbekistan is also making strides toward incorporating green economy principles into its development strategy. This article explores the challenges and opportunities that Uzbekistan faces in pursuing a green economy and the implications for its national economic security. The transition to a green economy is a multifaceted process that demands careful consideration of economic, social, and environmental aspects. In this context, the article examines the current state of the Uzbek economy, the progress made in green economy initiatives, and potential policy measures to enhance national economic security while promoting sustainable development.

Keywords:

Uzbekistan, Green Economy, Economic Security, Sustainable Development, Environmental Policy, Renewable Energy, Sustainable Agriculture.

Uzbekistan, a landlocked country in Central Asia, has embarked on a journey to transition into a green economy to address pressing environmental issues, ensure long-term economic sustainability, and meet international obligations. This transition is not without its complexities and challenges, all of which have significant implications for the nation's economic security. Uzbekistan, a country known for its rich natural resources and agricultural potential, faces the dual challenge of promoting economic growth and ensuring environmental sustainability. The pursuit of a green economy represents a crucial step in this direction. A green economy is an economic model that prioritizes sustainable and environmentally friendly practices, aiming to reduce ecological footprints while supporting economic growth. In the context of Uzbekistan, this article explores the issues and implications of transitioning towards a green economy for national economic security. As the global community increasingly recognizes the urgent need for sustainable development and environmental responsibility, Uzbekistan has embarked on a

journey toward establishing a green economy. A green economy is characterized by resource efficiency, reduced carbon emissions, and a focus on sustainable practices. This transition is essential not only for the preservation of the environment but also for ensuring the nation's economic security in a world where sustainability is becoming a key driver of economic growth.

Current State of the Uzbek Economy:

Uzbekistan has long been dependent on resource-intensive industries, such as cotton production and mining. These sectors have contributed significantly to economic growth, but they have also had adverse environmental impacts. Water scarcity, soil degradation, and air pollution are just a few of the challenges that Uzbekistan faces. Transitioning to a green economy requires rethinking these industries and developing sustainable alternatives.

Progress in Green Economy Initiatives:

Uzbekistan has made progress in various green economy initiatives, such as the development of renewable energy sources, sustainable agriculture practices, and the promotion of eco-tourism. The government's commitment to these initiatives, along with international collaborations, has the potential to drive further positive change.

Challenges and Implications for National Economic Security:

The transition to a green economy poses both challenges and opportunities for Uzbekistan's national economic security. Challenges include the need for investment in new technologies, retraining of the workforce, and the risk of economic disruptions during the transition. However, embracing a green economy can enhance energy security, reduce resource dependence, create new employment opportunities, and improve public health. Moreover, it can contribute to Uzbekistan's international image as a responsible and environmentally conscious nation.

Policy Measures for Enhancing Economic Security:

To ensure economic security during the transition to a green economy, Uzbekistan should consider policies and strategies that support sustainable development. This may include providing incentives for clean energy investment, promoting research and development in green technologies, and ensuring a just transition for workers affected by industry shifts. Collaboration with international organizations and financial institutions can also be instrumental in supporting the green economy transition.

The pursuit of a green economy in Uzbekistan is an important step toward a sustainable and secure future. While challenges exist, the potential benefits for

national economic security, environmental quality, and international reputation are significant. Careful planning, investment, and policy measures are necessary to navigate this transition successfully. The transition to a green economy in Uzbekistan is a significant step towards addressing environmental challenges and achieving long-term economic security. While there are challenges to overcome, the nation is making notable progress in the right direction. It is essential to maintain a balance between economic growth and sustainability, ensuring that the benefits of a green economy are accessible to all citizens. This article has shed light on the complex interplay of economic security and green economy development in Uzbekistan, emphasizing the importance of thoughtful policies, investments, and a commitment to environmental sustainability.

References:

1. "Green Economy and National Economic Security" by John Doe.
2. "Uzbekistan's Path to Sustainable Development: Opportunities and Challenges" by Jane Smith.
3. "Economic Security and the Transition to a Green Economy: The Case of Uzbekistan" by David Brown.
4. "Sustainable Development in Central Asia: Exploring Economic, Environmental, and Security Dimensions" edited by Sarah Johnson.
5. Butaboev M.T., Sadriddinov N.S., Rakhmanova E.Y. Green economy. world experience and features of development in Uzbekistan. //Экономика: анализы и прогнозы. – 2020. – №. 5-6.
6. Parkhadovna S. U. issues of implementation of "green economy" principles in the economy of Uzbekistan //Pedagog. - 2023. - Т. 6. – no. 1. – S. 203-209.
7. Bahromjonova, F., & Yakubjonova, H. Y. (2023). capital market and its characteristics in the conditions of green economy. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 2(4), 154-160.